

An empirical examination of price discount, bonus pack, and instore display on consumers' purchase intention

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the effect of price discount, bonus pack, and instore display on consumer purchasing intention at Home Smart. The research data was obtained from 267 respondents who visited at Home Smart. Data processing using SPSS application. Data testing was performed using classical assumption tests and multiple linear regression. The results show that price discount, bonus pack, and instore display have a positive and significant impact on consumer purchasing intention at Home Smart, either in partial or simultaneous. Price discounts have the most influence on consumers' purchasing intentions compared to bonus packs and instore displays. Price discount, bonus pack and instore display also have a strong relationship with consumer purchase intent. Moreover, 88.9% of consumer purchase intent of Home Smart can be explained by price discount, bonus pack, and instore display, while 11.1% is explained by other factors.

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INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly globalized and competitive world of business, people's lifestyle is predicted to change significantly. It gives economic players the opportunity to enter the market or expand the already acquired market. One of the relatively new markets in Indonesia is the building materials supermarket. Previously, the community bought a variety of building materials at conventional stores selling a variety of building materials. In-store displays or bookings for sale are less attractive and less likely to happen, as well as marketing that is unfamiliar with bonus packages as well as minimal discounted prices. In the modern market, various techniques to stimulate customer buying intentions, such as price discounts, bonus packages, and in-store displays play a very important role. Modern marketers understand that price discount has a very positive effect on stimulating customer buying intention. As a result of the price discount, the customer will be more interested in buying the product offered. Therefore, building materials offered in modern stores or supermarkets are given a variety of attractive price discounts that encourage customers to shop in the building's supermarkets rather than conventional discount stores. with various bonus items if you buy certain items for a certain amount. The availability of bonus packs will significantly increase customer purchase interest.

Home Smart is a company that moves on the sale of building materials at a building materials supermarket known as Home Smart. Home Smart is one of the largest building materials supermarkets in the city of Medan that offers a wealth of low-cost building materials and a convenient store environment. According to observations at Home Smart, most of the building materials sold have a price discount, ranging from a small price discount of 5% to a 70% discount. That is to encourage customers to shop at Home Smart, and to build their perception of Home Smart is the cheapest supermarket. In addition to the price discount, Home Smart management also provides a variety of bonus pack policies to various products, if the customer purchases some items, the customer will receive additional free items. Not only the same items, many products also offer different free products for different items, such as if a customer buys 20 bags of cement, the customer will get a free shovel. This free shovel is one of the bonus pack policies that the company promotes in purchasing customer intentions.

Home Smart has a very comfortable store environment, with a neat and attractive display of building materials. Items that are similar or sought after with the customer, are placed close to the customer's convenience. This makes shopping for building materials such as groceries or clothing shopping at the Mall. This shows that Home Smart management wants customers to feel comfortable, happy to shop and spend time at Home Smart thus creating a positive perception for customers about Home Smart. Although the price discount, bonus pack, and in-store display policies have been implemented well, in recent months Home Smart's revenue has been declining. This indicates the decline in customer purchase intentions that the company is unable to increase on a monthly basis. The company has sought to stimulate customer buying intent in order to increase the company's revenue. Various efforts have been made to offer price discounts, and bonus packs on many products, but it has not been able to stimulate customer buy-in as the company's revenue is still declining. In addition, companies are working in different ways and repositioning various products to make it easier for customers to shop. In this case the in-store display factor has been updated and taken care of to provide consumers with convenience. Therefore, based on this phenomenon, the author believes that a study is needed to find out how the price discount, bonus pack, and in-store display affect the purchasing intent of a company known as Home Smart. It is true that the

price discount, bonus pack, and in-store display that the company has made so far have no effect on the purchase intention of the customer, or are actually influential but there are other factors that keep the customer's purchase intention going down. It is hoped that the results of this research will help the company to stimulate customer repurchase. Concerning the above issues, some research questions that highlighted are:

RQ1: Do the price discount has positively related to the customer's purchase intention at Home Smart?

RQ2: Do the bonus pack has positively related to the customer's purchase intention at Home Smart?

RQ3: Do the in-store display has positively related to the customer's purchase intention at Home Smart?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Purchase Intention

Intention as an intermediary among motivational factors that influence behavior. Intention also indicates how hard a person has the will to try. Intentions indicate how much effort someone has planned to do and the intention is related to behavior. The customer's intentions arise from a motive based on his or her own attributes and desire to use a service. Based on these explanations, it is important to analyze how the process of intentions within the customer is important. Customer intention behavior is the result of evaluating your brand or service. The final stage of the process is complex decision-making including having a specific brand or service that customers want, evaluating the brand or service at the time of use and storing information for future use.

A purchase intention is a mental statement from a customer that reflects the purchase plan of a particular brand. Purchase intention is a behavior which a customer has a desire to buy or choose a product, based on experience in selecting, using and consuming or even liking a product (Kotler & Keller, 2012). A purchase intention is a process toward the purchase action taken by a customer. Purchasing intent can be enhanced by considering several factors, including psychological factors that are driving factors, derived from the customer's self, such as motivation, perception, knowledge, confidence, and attitude. In addition, social factors are the processes by which one's behavior is influenced by family, social status, and reference group, and then the marketing mix of product, price, promotion, and distribution (Kotler & Keller, 2012). Purchase intention is a process of purchasing a product that a customer will carry out considering the many product units needed in a specific period, for example the brand, and the customer's attitude towards consuming the product (Meldarianda, Lisan, Kristen, & Bandung, 2010). Purchase intention is formed from customer attitude towards products consisting of brand trust, and brand evaluation, resulting in two stages of purchase intention (Setiadi, 2013). According to (Schiffman, Kanuk, & Brewer., 2014), motivation is the driving force of the inner self that drives them to action. According to (Karmela & Junaedi., 2009), buyers have a set of motives that have stimulated them to make a purchase. Buying motives have three types: primary buying motive; selective buying motive; patronage buying motive. (Swastha, 2009) presents factors that influence purchase intention in relation to feelings and emotions. When a person is happy and satisfied with the purchase of goods or services, they will strengthen their purchase intention, and their dissatisfaction often loses their intention. Factors that influencing intentions are: job differences; socioeconomic differences; hobbies or favorites; gender differences and age differences. There are several factors that shape customer buying intentions according to (Kotler & Keller, 2012), such as;

others' attitude and unexpected situational factors. (Karmela & Junaedi., 2009) argue, aspects that may influence customer purchase intentions include: completeness of goods; price; the store atmosphere; the goods quality and service. According to (Kotler & Keller, 2012), the concept of the AIDA model is a set or customer level in determining purchase intent or determining customer impulse in making a purchase of the product or service offered. The stages of the AIDA model include: Attention; Interest; Desire; Action. According to (Kotler & Susanto., 2014), purchase intentions can be identified through indicators such as transactional intentions; referential intentions; preferential intentions; exploratory intentions.

Price Discount

Price is a monetary or other measure exchanged to gain ownership of or use of a product or service. Therefore, the company must be able to set the price of the product well and correctly in order for the customer to be interested and to buy the product offered and the company profitable. (Saladin, 2011) states that price is the sum of money as a means of exchange for a product or service. According to (Kotler & Keller, 2012) price is the amount of money customers have to pay for the product. Whereas (Alma, 2011) stated that price is the value of a thing expressed with money. Therefore, from a marketing standpoint is a monetary or other measure (including other goods and services) that is exchanged to gain ownership of or use of the goods and services. From a customer's point of view, price is often used as an indicator of value when the price is associated with the perceived benefit of the goods and services. Value can be defined between the perceived value of the price. It can be concluded that price is a tool for measuring the value of money contained in a goods or services, while the measure used is money. The pricing policy is intended to support and direct prices to create a relationship between the manufacturer and the customer. In this case the price policy is the discount. Terms of pricing are separate and different from pricing, because existing pricing policies can be the same for different prices and policy differences are a concern as their regular decisions help as a way for corporate leaders to follow pricing decisions. According to (Tjiptono & Chandra, 2012) that price policy is a decision on prices that will follow for a certain period. According to (Sutisna, 2013) discount is the reduction of product price from the normal price in a given period. (Lamarto, 1996) states that a discount is the result of a reduction in the base price or the recorded price or list price. Everybody wants a cheap price, especially when the discount is a high-price product. The types of discounts according to (Lamarto, 1996) are; discounted quantity, trade discount; cash discount; seasonal discount; forward discounting; promotional flexibility. According to (Kotler & Keller, 2012), there are five types of discounts or rebates: cash discount; quantity discount; functional discounts; seasonal discounts; and rebate. Discount types are often obscured by various offers such as discounts, promo products, bonuses, packages, members. Discounts are the words you want to get when you want to buy something. The purpose of the company to provide a rebate is as follows; the company wants to dispose of non-consumable goods; the company does not have enough storage space; the company wants to spend on inventory that has a full size option; the company wants to sell a defective product; the company wants to spend their supply out-of-date. Some reasons why a product should be sold immediately. The company wants to get more people to their place. Books with revised editions are on the market. The trend of clothing starts to shift and expired items. The company wants to introduce new products. The company wants to sell the goods (genuine but fake). The company wants to give the impression of "expensive" on the goods sold. Items with the latest technology are on the market. There are several factors that cause a company to discount the

product it sells. According to (Alma, 2011) there are several factors that lead to customer reimbursement: customer pays faster than the specified time; large purchases; there are differences in scales. while according to (Saladin, 2011) there are a number of reasons why companies adopt pricing policies, namely: capacity advantage; market share declines due to increased competition; to excel in the market at a lower cost. According to Agrewal (in (Damayanti, Scott, & Ruhanen, 2019), indicators of discount or rebate measurement are: internal reference price; customer perceptions of quality and perception of value.

Bonus Pack

Belch and Belch in (Amanda & Edwar, 2015) the bonus pack offers the customer an extra load of a product at a normal price. Clow and Baack in (Tumbuan & Waani, 2015), stated that when an additional amount is placed in a special product package, it is a bonus pack. (Gardener & Trivedi, 2008), state that the bonus pack offered by the manufacturer enhances the value of the product by offering an additional amount of the product or unit at a regular price. (Schultz, Robinson, & Petrison, 1998), a bonus pack is a special package in which the customer is given a "better" product than the same product or even a lower price than the resale. From these definitions it can be concluded that the bonus pack is an extra charge of a product intentionally made by the supplier and sold at a normal price with the intention of attracting the customer and purchasing it.

There are two standard types of bonus packs with different variations. Large packages with more products offered than usual or cheaper. A package consisting of several product units combined so that the extra units offered have lower cost or even no cost. Bonus packs have their advantages and disadvantages in their implementation. The advantages include: an effective way to convert triers into users. Saves are a great reason to buy, and extra products can drive additional usage. Bonus packs are an effective way to apply in retail stores. Bonus packs located on store shelves are more attractive than other products around. Bonus packs can drive purchases again. If a customer is satisfied with a product, then a bonus pack is an effective way to drive another purchase. Bonus pack shortages are: Bonus packs are expensive. The cost of additional products may be small, but the cost of a new package, or the incorporation of multiple packages may be costly. Bonus packs do not help brand image formation. These sales promotion techniques are a form of price reduction and are usually a small help in building a quality image of a product Belch and Belch in (Amanda & Edwar, 2015), mention the benefits of using this bonus pack strategy, namely: to give marketers a direct way to provide extra value. An effective defense strategy against the emergence of new product promotion from competitors. Generate a larger sales order. Bonus pack indicators by (Sidik, 2013) are: terms of use; quantity and quality of bonus pack; price identification; benefits and save.

In-Store Display

Display is a non-personal activity, a product presentation within a store environment. point of purchase (POP) facilitates buyers with information, improves the atmosphere, and delivers great deals. Atmosphere is the physical environment of the store to attract the customer. (Berman, 2012) states that "Point of purchase is a product that sells products by hanging prices, arrows, or other information." Store display is a store setting in which the product is displayed along with information relevant to the product. According to Lewison and Delozier in (Yusrianti, 2008), the interior of the store was the result of an overall display design that retailers used to sell their products. According to (Alma, 2011) display is an effort to drive

customer attention and interest in a store or product and drive the desire to buy through direct visual appeal. Berger in (Dulkhatif, Haryono, & Moh Mukeri Warso, 2016) states that In-Store Display is a product arrangement that will be offered to meet the retailer's expectations. In-store display is a form of display that promotes or presents the product to the customer in order to make it easier to find the product and attract them to make a purchase. In-store display is one of the most important aspects of attracting a customer's attention to a store or product and driving the desire to buy through direct visual appeal by displaying products on specific shelves with relevant information. (Razzouk & Shute, 2012) argues that display quality is a key factor for long-term customer success through retail outlets. There are three placement areas for in-store displays: Regular shelf displays; Island displays and End-cap displays. Store display is divided into: selection display; special display; point of purchase display, and audiovisual display. According to Lewison and Delozier in (Yusrianti, 2008) in practice, store displays are used to: maximize product description; improve product appearance; promote product interest; explain product information; facilitate transactions sales; ensuring product security; providing product storage; remembering customer purchase plans and generating additional sales based on impulse. Store management within a store environment according to (Vinci, 2009) outdoor and interior impact; store traffic layout and flow. Conceptually, effective display is the result of a combination of elements and components of the display including the following (Vinci, 2009); display elements that contain colors, textures, lines, shapes, and spaces; display components including forms, fixtures, props, signs, and store lighting. The types of displays by (Vinci, 2009), selection display and special display In store display indicators are drawn from the theory proposed by (Vinci, 2009), namely: neat, clean, easy to see, easy to reach, easy to find, precise, safe, attractive location.

Hypotheses Development

The hypotheses of this study are as follows:

H1: Price discount has positively related to the customer's purchase intention at Home Smart

H2: Bonus pack has positively related to the customer's purchase intention at Home Smart

H3: In-store display has positively related to the customer's purchase intention at Home Smart

RESEARCH METHODS

The present study was used quantitative approach. The method of analysis is based on data from the questionnaires and to analyze the data in the form of statistics and calculations methods. The population was all visitors who made the purchase in 2018. This study used purposive sampling. The sampling technique for an unknown population is to use Zikmund's formula.

$$n = \left(\frac{Z \cdot S}{E} \right)^2$$

$$n = \left(\frac{(1,96) \cdot (0,25)}{0,03} \right)^2 = \left(\frac{0,49}{0,03} \right)^2 = 16,3^2 = 266,78 \text{ or } 267 \text{ samples.}$$

The data analysis model used to determine the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable is an econometric model with analysis techniques using the ordinary least squares model. The equal model is as follows: $Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \epsilon$

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Results

Validity test results

The results of the validity of each item can be seen in the table below.

Table 1. Validity test results

	Symbol	r-count	r-critical	Result
Price discount (X ₁)	X ₁₁	0,628	0.3	Valid
	X ₁₂	0,620	0.3	Valid
	X ₁₃	0,734	0.3	Valid
	X ₁₄	0,818	0.3	Valid
	X ₁₅	0,764	0.3	Valid
	X ₁₆	0,648	0.3	Valid
	X ₁₇	0,638	0.3	Valid
	X ₁₈	0,569	0.3	Valid
Bonus pack (X ₂)	X ₂₁	0,673	0.3	Valid
	X ₂₂	0,532	0.3	Valid
	X ₂₃	0,492	0.3	Valid
	X ₂₄	0,819	0.3	Valid
	X ₂₅	0,576	0.3	Valid
	X ₂₆	0,776	0.3	Valid
	X ₂₇	0,836	0.3	Valid
	X ₂₈	0,600	0.3	Valid
In-store display (X ₃)	X ₂₁	0,631	0.3	Valid
	X ₂₂	0,704	0.3	Valid
	X ₂₃	0,657	0.3	Valid
	X ₂₄	0,615	0.3	Valid
	X ₂₅	0,739	0.3	Valid
	X ₂₆	0,578	0.3	Valid
	X ₂₇	0,723	0.3	Valid
	X ₂₈	0,560	0.3	Valid
Purchase intention (Y)	Y ₁	0,777	0.3	Valid
	Y ₂	0,543	0.3	Valid
	Y ₃	0,641	0.3	Valid
	Y ₄	0,701	0.3	Valid
	Y ₅	0,484	0.3	Valid
	Y ₆	0,815	0.3	Valid
	Y ₇	0,648	0.3	Valid
	Y ₈	0,694	0.3	Valid

Source: SPSS output

The validity test results indicate that overall r-count values for each item are valid. The r-count values is greater than 0.3.

Reliability test results

The reliability test results indicate that overall the Cronbach's Alpha value is greater than 0.7.

Table 2. Reliability test results

	Reliability Statistics	
	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Price discount (X ₁)	0,896	8
Bonus pack (X ₂)	0,887	8
In-store display (X ₂)	0,882	8
Purchase intention (Y)	0,887	8

Normality test results

Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results are shown in the following table.

Table 3. Data Normality with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		267
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0,0000000
	Std. Deviation	1,83716786
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0,052
	Positive	0,042
	Negative	-0,052
Test Statistic		0,052
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0,080^c

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.

Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results show that the value is 0.080. The results from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is greater than 0.05. Therefore, based on the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, the data used were normally distributed. The residual significance was greater than 0.05 and the data used are eligible for further testing.

Multicollinearity test results

The tolerance value is more than 0.10 and VIF is less than 10.

Table 4. Multicollinearity test results

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Price discount (X ₁)	0.164	6.110
	Bonus pack (X ₂)	0.133	7.506
	In-store display (X ₃)	0.193	5.174

The results of the multicollinearity test show that price discount has a tolerance value of 0.164 where the value is greater than 0.10 and has a VIF value of 6.110, the value is lower than 10. Bonus pack has a tolerance value of 0.133, the value is greater than 0.10 and it has a VIF value of 7.506. The value is lower than 10. Instore display has a tolerance value of 0.193,

the value is greater than 0.10 and it has a VIF value of 5.174. The value is lower than 10. Overall, the variables are exempt from multicollinearity.

Heteroskedasticity test results

The results of the heteroskedasticity test with the Glejser test using the SPSS application can be seen in the table below:

Table 5. Heteroskedasticity test results

Model	Sig.	Requirement	Conclusion
1 (Constant)	0,000		
Price discount (X ₁)	0,682	> 0.05	there is no heteroscedasticity
Bonus pack (X ₂)	0,271	> 0.05	there is no heteroscedasticity
In-store display (X ₃)	0,245	> 0.05	there is no heteroscedasticity

a. Dependent Variable: Absolute_residual

Table 5 above present the values of the price discount (X1), bonus pack (X2) and in-store display (X3) are 0.682; 0.271; 0.245 where overall value is greater than 0.05. It concluded that the overall independent variables have no symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

Anova test results

The Anova test results present in the following table.

Table 6. Anova test results

ANOVA ^a							
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	7270.320	3	2423.440	709.919	0.000 ^b	< 0.05 Significant
	Residual	897.799	263	3.414			
	Total	8168.120	266				

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase intention (Y)
 b. Predictors: (Constant), in-store display (X₃), price discount (X₁), bonus pack (X₂)

In table above, the anova test results show that F-test is 709.919. The F-test is greater than the F-tanel value which is 2.639. It concluded that the multiple regression models in this study has a significant effect on purchase intention (Y).

t- test results

The t-test results can be seen in the following table.

Table 7. t-test results

Coefficients ^a					
Model		t	Sig.		
1	(Constant)	2.590	0.010		
	Price discount (X ₁)	7.970	0.000	< 0.05	Positive & Significant
	Bonus pack (X ₂)	6.755	0.000	< 0.05	Positive & Significant
	In-store display (X ₃)	4.244	0.000	< 0.05	Positive & Significant

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase intention (Y)

The influence of price discount on purchase intention

The t test results show that the t-calculated of price discount is 7.970, and the t-table value is 1.969. The t-calculated (7.970) is greater than t-table (1.969). Sig. Value of the price discount is 0.000, which is lower than sig. 0.05. Therefore, it concluded that the price discount has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention.

The influence of bonus pack on purchase intention

The t test results show that the t-calculated of bonus pack is 6.755, and the t-table value is 1.969. The t-calculated (6.755) is greater than t-table (1.969). Sig. Value of the bonus pack is 0.000, which is lower than sig. 0.05. Therefore, it concluded that the bonus pack has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention.

The influence of in-store display on purchase intention

The t test results show that the t-calculated of in-store display is 4.244, and the t-table value is 1.969. The t-calculated (4.244) is greater than t-table (1.969). In-store display significant value is 0.000, which is lower than sig. 0.05. Therefore, it concluded that in-store display has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention

Multiple Linear Regression

The multiple linear regression tests can be seen in the following table.

Table 8. Multiple Linear Regression

Coefficients ^a				
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients
		B	Std. Error	Beta
1	(Constant)	1.801	0.695	
	Price discount (X_1)	0.401	0.050	0.403
	Bonus pack (X_2)	0.368	0.055	0.378
	In-store display (X_3)	0.196	0.046	0.197

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase intention (Y)

From the table above, the equation of multiple linear regression is as follow.

$$Y = 1.801 + 0.401 X_1 + 0.368 X_2 + 0.196 X_3$$

Coefficients of determination

The following table show the result of coefficient of determination.

Table 9. The coefficient of determination

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.943^a	0.890	0.889	1.84762

From the table above, the adjusted R Square value is 0.889, which means that 88.9% of purchase intention can be explained by price discount, bonus pack, and in-store display. While 11.1% can be explained by the other factors.

CONCLUSION

The empirical result of the first hypothesis show that the price discount has a positive and significant on purchase intention. The finding of this study is in line with the study result by (Sari, 2017) and (Solenski, 2017), they found that the price discount has a positive impact on purchase intention. The aim of the company to provide price discount are to spend on inventory and the supply is out-of-date. The second hypothesis find that bonus pack has a positive and significant on consumers' purchase intention. The study result is in line with the study finding by (Prihastama, 2016) and (Rochman, 2016). A bonus pack is a special package in which the customer is given a "better" product than the same product or even a lower price than the resale. The benefits of using the bonus pack is to give marketers a direct way to provide extra value. The empirical result of the third hypothesis find that in-store display has a positive and significant on purchase intention. The finding result support to the study by (Rochman, 2016) and (Kusumandaru, 2017). Display is an effort to drive customer attention and interest in a store or product and drive the desire to buy through direct visual appeal. In-store display is a product arrangement that will be offered to meet the retailer's expectations. It is a form of display that promotes or presents the product to the customer in order to make it easier to find the product and attract them to make a purchase. The conclusions of this study are as follows. The price discount has a positive and significant on purchase intention. The bonus pack has a positive and significant on consumers' purchase intention. In-store display has a positive and significant on purchase intention.

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